

Teaching Vocabulary to B1 Level Students

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Abstract

Teaching vocabulary at the intermediate (B1) level is a difficult task because students require more attention than their enthusiasm for learning. According to the CEFR, B1 level candidates in ESL learning (i.e., intermediate independent users of the target language) are required to understand the key point of straightforward, normal feedback on familiar matters experienced on a daily basis at work, education, etc. Additionally, they are required to be in a situation to manage most circumstances prone to emerge when they are utilizing the objective language at home or abroad, in different social settings. They can create a straightforward intelligible book on subjects of individual or social interest and they can depict encounters and occasions, dreams, expectations, and aspirations and momentarily offer reasons and clarifications for thoughts and plans.

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INTRODUCTION.

In this day and age, the interest to the experts who is ace in unknown dialects is creating step by step in our free republic now. Specifically, English is additionally viewed as one of the requesting dialects of our life. Obviously, it's anything but a mystery, that there is being focused on the showing English language. To make an agreeably grew, profoundly taught, present day thinking youthful age the main the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov marked a Decree "On measures to additionally improve the learning arrangement of unknown dialects." Currently, the field of English Language Teaching started to address phonetic and social variety; as opposed to zeroing in on training perspectives identified with the English language. Presumably, English is the most famous unknown dialect. Numerous Uzbek individuals wish to learn for instructive, monetary and social reasons, a reality that applies to numerous other non-English talking nations also.

Generally, vocabulary used to be offered to students as records and jargon guidance has zeroed in on having understudies look into word implications and retain them. This instructing approach gives just the surface and transient learning of words. The Texas Reading Initiate found that students who simply memorize word meanings frequently have troubles applying the information in definitions and often make mistakes about the meaning.

A word utilized in various settings may have various implications: hence basically learning meanings of a word without instances of where and when the word happens won't assist students with completely understanding its significance. Learning an isolated list of words without reference to the context is a memorization exercise that makes it difficult for learners to use the words in spoken and written language.

Looking at the context in which the word appears seems to be the best way of learning vocabulary and learn how its meaning relates to the words around it. In addition, a methodology that incorporates definitions, just as its utilization in the content, can create full and adaptable information on word implications.

When students are given several sentences that use a word in different ways they begin to see how a meaning of words can change and shift depending on its context. Learners need to see words in different contexts in order to learn them thoroughly.

Honey field stresses the importance of context by arguing that even with a functional vocabulary of 3000 most frequently occurring items in English learners will not still know approximately 20 percent of items, they will come across in an unsimplified text.

Too much dictionary work can kill all interests in reading and even interfere with comprehension" because learners become more concerned with individual items and less aware of the context, which gives them meaning. It is also results in every slow and inefficient reading "

Therefore, good learners often acquire much of their vocabulary through independent reading are learned through context. In any case, Watanable cases that "Albeit coincidental learning of jargon through setting is conceivable, it isn't generally productive"

Indeed, learning vocabulary must be meaningful to students. This occurs when a learner is able to relate new words to his/her prior knowledge or scheme. Schema is defined by Pearson and Spiro as little pictures or associations you conjure up in your head when you read a word or sentence.

The rich literary context for each word not only provides a literary context, but also exposes students to fiction and non-fiction by various authors.

These four stages of word knowledge were summarized by Dale and Oroiroke as follows:

1. I have never seen it before

2. I have never heard of it, but I do not know what it means.
3. I recognized it in the context- it has something to do with...
4. I know it.

Seeing vocabulary in rich context provided by the authentic texts, rather than isolated vocabulary drills produced strong vocabulary learning. Rich and strong vocabulary instruction goes beyond definitional knowledge; it gets students actively engaged in using and thinking about word meaning, associates with other words, guessing from the context. If the students decide that a term is worth guessing, they will use Nation and Coady's five-step procedure:

1. Determine the parts of the speech of unknown words
2. Look at immediate context and simplify it if necessary.
3. Look at the wider context. This involves inspecting the proviso with the obscure word and its relationship to the encompassing conditions and sentences..
4. Guess the meaning of the unknown word
5. Check that the guess is correct.

The couple of investigations of speculating words from setting demonstrate that an enormous extent of the obscure words can be effectively managed thusly.

As it was mentioned before, Linda Diamond and Linda Galton pointed out that one of the words of learning strategies is contextual, involves inferring the meaning of unfamiliar word by examining the text surrounding it. Instruction in contextual analysis generally involves teaching students to use both general and specific types of context clues.

Several writes describe various types of clues that can provide information to help in guessing. Brown lists definitions, learner's experience of the world contrast, interference and analysis. Steinberg lists grammar, punctuation, definition, contrast, connectives, reference words, word analysis and the learner's experience and common sense. But all these approaches lack in semantic procedure to follow. Only Chanrasegaran uses a questioning procedure to guide learners in guessing, but this is dependent on the teacher's choice of questions.

As stated in the Texas Reading Initiative, these are some techniques for enhancing students' awareness of the importance of context clues:

- Exercise simple text-reading techniques such as using meaning cues.
- Explain how, where, and why context is helpful in determining word meanings.
- Provide guided practice in using context.
- Remind students to apply the skill when reading on their own.

Long and Nation agreed with the Texas Reading Initiative's statements by giving steps that are needed in the strategy. They are:

- Part of the speech;
- Immediate context;
- Wider context;
- Word parts

- They need to know the meaning of the parts
- They should have the option to see an association between the importance of the parts and the word reference significance of the new word.

So vocabulary knowledge involves not only the definitional meaning of a word but also the knowledge to use words in an appropriate context. If they have this knowledge they will be able to guess the meaning of a word from the contexts.

In this procedure several methods can be our assistants: mnemonic technique, context clues and so on.

When teachers want to success in teaching vocabulary they should choose appropriate text to teach. Choosing the text is one of the problems of vocabulary teaching.

Most people agree that vocabulary ought to be taught in context (Nilsen 1976; Chastain 1976; Rivers 1968). Words instructed in detachment are by and large not held. Also, to get a handle on the full importance of a word or expression, understudies should know about the etymological climate in which the word or expression shows up. Setting a good context which is interesting, plausible, vivid and has relevance to the lives of the learners, is an essential prerequisite for vocabulary teaching as it helps in both drawing in the consideration of the students and normally creating the objective jargon. Keeping up the unique situation and ensuring the language encompassing the setting is not difficult to appreciate, the instructor should begin inspiring the objective jargon.

Every word has its origin and its story of how it gets its current meaning. Because of its physical and meaningful origin, the etymology of a word is often found much easier to be comprehended than the bare linguistic symbol and its present semantic meaning. So, whenever we teach an English word that is completely strange, we can ask students to look it up in a dictionary or other reference books, and or surf on the internet to find its origin. The intriguing stories behind a word's introduction to the world can be a generally excellent update for understudies to recall the specific word. Thus, learning the etymology of a word will certainly promote students' comprehension of new words.

By drawing pictures. It is a simple and speedy procedure of acquainting jargon with the students. For understudies, drawing can be a great medium to clarify jargon. It isn't required that an instructor should be a specialist in drawing pictures precisely. He can draw rough sketches to make an idea clear.

Basic sketches will often work well. You can even have understudies do their own drawings, which further builds up their comprehension of the jargon. Near words and relational words can be clarified by basic representations. Pictures of numerous kinds and tones can be utilized effectively to show the importance of words and sentences. Drawings can be utilized to clarify the importance of things, activities, characteristics and relations.

In recognizing part of speech there can be done "What does what?" exercise. All the guessing procedures described so far focus on linguistic information that is present within a text. There are other important sources of information. These include knowledge that learners already have about particular words through having met them before knowledge of the subject that they are reading about (this may be knowledge that is gained through the learners' first language) and knowledge of the conceptual structure of the topic.

When learners meet an unknown word and discover its meaning, they may wish to make an extra effort to remember word.

Mnemonic strategies are the systematic procedures for enhancing memory. The word mnemonic comes from Mnemosyne, the name of the Greek goddess of memory. The keyword method, mnemonic strategy, has been shown to be effective with students who have learning difficulties and those who are at risk for educational failure. According to the National Reading Panel (2000), the keyword method may lead to significant improvement in students' recall of new vocabulary words.

In this technique, the learners create an unusual association between the word form and its meaning. For example, an Uzbek learner of English wants to remember the meaning of the English word "parrot".

First, the learner thinks of an Uzbek word “parit”, which means “a ditch”. This is a keyboard.

Second, imagine a parrot lying in a ditch. The more striking and unusual the image, the more effective it is.

The keyboard technique, while being very effective for learning foreign vocabulary, is best considered as only one of several learning techniques that can be used to master foreign vocabulary. Other possible techniques which try to develop both form and meaning associations are the use of analysis into affixes and roots, and mnemonics like “A pintu (door) is used for going into something. Craike and Lock chart mentioned that the general principle of the “levels of processing” theory is that the more the words are analyzed and enriched by associates or images, the longer they will stay in the memory.

Although the keyboard technique seems rather unusual at first sight, its effectiveness lies in its association of both formal and meaning elements of the new word by the use of aural and imagery cues.

Delany, Paivio and Desrocher analyzed fifty studies of keyboard technique. They reached the following conclusion¹.

1. The keyboard technique helps the learning of the foreign vocabulary and superior to other techniques, such as rote repetition, placing vocabulary in a meaningful sentence, and using or synonyms.

2. The use of the keyboard technique is not restricted to concrete nouns but can be used with verbs, abstract nouns and adjectives.

3. The use of the keyboard technique is restricted to adults. It tends to be utilized with youngsters however youthful as three years on the off chance that they may be helped a ton in utilizing the strategy.

4. It is not still clear if it is best for the teacher to provide the keyboards or for learners to make their own. Where learners need help, it will be best if teacher provides it. It seems to be the best for the teacher to provide the linking picture if possible. There are difficulties in doing this, however, if the learners think their own key words.

5. The keyboard technique does not slow down recall of the meaning of foreign words.

6. Very little experimentation has been done on the effect of the keyboard technique on pronunciation and spelling. No negative effects have yet been found. They point out that there is no reason to expect the keyword technique does not have any in-built mnemonic tricks to help spelling or pronunciation.

7. Most experiments with the keyword technique have looked at receptive vocabulary learning. It means being able to recall the meaning when the foreign word is provided. The form of keyword must have a close connection with the form of the foreign word. If care is taken with this, then the keyword technique is good for productive vocabulary learning.

8. One difficulty with the keyword technique is that it is often difficult to think of keywords that sound like a foreign word. The more imagination you have, the more useful the techniques.

The keyword technique is not the only method that can be used in vocabulary teaching. There is another way which can be very useful in learning vocabulary. This is through roots and affixes. Knowledge of Latin affixes and roots has two values for learners of English. It can be used to help the learning of unfamiliar words by relating these words to known words, or to know prefixes, suffixes. And it can be used as a way of checking whether an unfamiliar has been correctly guessed from the context.

Some Latin prefixes occur in many different words. For example, the prefix ad- in its various forms occurs in 433 of the 20.000 most frequent words in the Teacher's word book by Thorndike and Lorge. Brow tabulated the most important prefixes and root elements and compiled a list of 20 prefixes and 14 root elements which is related to 14.000 words in Webster's Collegiate Dictionary and a researched 100,000 words in an unabridged dictionary. These have been combined into 14 matters words.

By learning master words and the meaning of their parts, learners will know the most useful prefixes and roots. In making use of prefixes and roots, learners need three skills: they need to be able to break new words onto parts so that the affixes and roots revealed.

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